

A SURVEY OF HIGH TEMPERATURE PROPERTIES OF POLYIMIDE COMPOSITES

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Summary

A survey of the commercially available polyimides has been made. The chemistry, processing, and typical mechanical properties of this polymeric family will be presented.

Introduction

The search for high-temperature polymers for use as functional resins (e.g., coatings and sealants) and as structural resins (e.g., adhesives, composite matrices, and foams) began in the mid-1950's. Early work on high temperature polymers dealt only with thermal stability. Little or no attention was paid to cost, processability, performance, or actual end use applications. Even though a lot of the new materials synthesized exhibited excellent thermal stability, they could not be processed. These earlier materials were commonly referred to as poly brick dusts. As work progressed, the neglected factors started playing an increasingly significant role in the design of materials for polymeric composites.¹

The ideal high temperature polymeric system for use as a production-type laminating resin for structural composites should have the following desirable characteristics: easy tape and prepreg preparation; good shelf-life; acceptable tack and drape; acceptable quality control procedures; no volatile evolution during processing; void-free matrices; good mechanical performance over the desired temperature and time ranges, and environmental conditions; acceptable repair ability; and cost effectiveness. Also, the high temperature ranges for the composite materials were also being specified; i.e., continuous use at 500°F; continuous use at 600°F; 50% retention of room temperature mechanical properties after being exposed to 530°C (986°F) for 80 hours; and continuous use at 600°F with short term excursions (seconds) to 1,100°F.^{1,2,3}

Today, no commercially available system exists which offers all of the above desirable features for a laminating resin in high temperature structural composites. However, a few commercially available polymeric systems represent a compromise of these desirable properties. Of these polymeric systems, the one based on polyimide chemistry has shown the most promise. Out of all the many chemistries explored, the polyimides and their modifications are the major ones currently being actively pursued by various government and industrial laboratories both from a synthetic and fabrication point of view. In reality, more developmental effort has been directed towards polyimides than all other high temperature polymeric systems combined. The major emphasis on the polyimides has been attributed to their ability to produce acceptable tapes and prepregs; to yield in most cases, laminates with little or no voids; and to produce laminates with good mechanical properties over the desired temperature and time ranges, and environmental conditions. The drawbacks associated with the polyimides are high processing temperatures, pressures, and times; nonacceptable repairability; and high cost.¹ The purpose of this survey is to provide the reader with an introduction to the chemistries, processing, and mechanical properties of the polyimides that are currently commercially available as matrix resins for composites.

Chemistry of the Polyimides

The characteristic moiety built into the polymer backbone of the polyimides is:

The reaction sequence to prepare a polyimide normally involves a two-step reaction. The first step is the reaction between a diamine and a dianhydride to form an intermediate poly(amic acid), while the second consists of a cyclodehydration of the poly(amic acid) to yield the desired polyimide and water as a by-product. These two steps can be illustrated by the following reaction scheme:

In most cases, both the diamine and dianhydride are aromatic in nature. The combination of the imide and aromatic moieties within the polymer backbone tends to increase the overall thermal stability of the polymer.

In 1955, the E. I. duPont de Nemours and Company was granted the first of several patents on aromatic polyimides.^{1,4} The major portion of this earlier development first involved the reaction of pyromellitic dianhydride (1,2,4,5-benzenetetracarboxylic dianhydride), PMDA, with 4,4'-oxydianiline (4-aminophenyl ether), ODA, to form the poly(amic acid) precursor which was soluble, then the insoluble polyimide was formed via a cyclodehydration reaction. In addition to using ODA, 4,4'-methylenedianiline, MDA, and phenylenediamine were used to react with pyromellitic dianhydride to form polyimides. The poly(amic acid) lacquers of the above chemistries exhibited problems in shelf-life storage due to hydrolytic instability. Also, the polyimide showed a general lack of melt flow during processing. After additional developmental work variations of the poly(amic acid) and polyimide chemistries were made commercially available by DuPont starting in the sixties. Examples of these materials were Pyre[®] ML, a lacquer resin mainly used for electronic applications; Vespel[®] a filled or unfilled

polyimide molded by DuPont and machined to specifications by their customers; and Kapton® a polyimide film.⁵

Monsanto expanded the availability of polyimides to the market place by introducing a series of material under the name Skybond. The major difference between Monsanto's and DuPont's polyimides was the dianhydride used. Monsanto used 3,3',4,4'-benzophenone tetracarboxylic dianhydride, BTDA.^{6,7} The polyimides based on this dianhydride tended to lend itself more to a material which could be made into tapes and prepregs better because of its solubility and melt flow characteristics.

In order to meet the material requirements of NASA and the Air Force as brought about by the onset of the space age, workers in the field thought that by changing the nature of the polyimides from a thermoplastic to a thermoset, materials could be made which processed easier and could have higher temperature capabilities than the existing polyimides. The formation of the thermosetting polyimides was achieved by TRW during the late sixties.⁸ TRW used the previously known polyimide technology and polymer principles to prepare low molecular weight oligomers and then end capping the oligomers with reactive sites of unsaturation. The end capping was accomplished by using a monofunctional anhydride with a nadic moiety. These nadic sites of unsaturation were thermally polymerized into a crosslinked network. This technology developed by TRW became known as P13N with P standing for polyimide, the 13 representing the average oligomer molecular weight of 1300, and N referring to the nadic end cappers.¹ This innovation showed a marked improvement in the processability of polyimides as matrix resins for composites, however, the resultant cured material was extremely brittle.

NASA - Lewis Research Center improved on the P13N chemistry developed by TRW. Their version was coined PMR-15, Polymerization of Monomeric Reactants - 1500 average molecular weight between end cappers.^{9,10} The improvements in chemistry and processability of PMR-15 were realized by increasing the average molecular weight between the end cappers and by using a lacquer of the monomers for prepregging. The monomeric lacquer was formed by first forming the half esters of the dianhydride and anhydride end capper and then mixing the diamine into the resultant solution using the proper stoichiometric amounts of each. These improvements resulted in a lacquer with a high solid loading which deemed itself better for a prepregging operation and upon cured a laminate which was less brittle than ones obtained from P13N chemistries. The thermal activities associated with the processing of PMR-15 to a final crosslinked structure consist of first removal of the residual alcoholic solvent, removal of water and alcohol by-products of reactions to form the polyimide from the monomeric reactants and finally the crosslinking reaction of the unsaturated end cappers.

In order to simplify the thermal events of the thermosetting reaction and improve on the processability of the thermosetting polyimides NASA - Langley Research Center made several modifications of the PMR-15 chemistry. Langley used only a stoichiometric amount of alcohol to form the half esters of the dianhydride and anhydride end capper and the diamine was replaced by a liquid oligomeric amine.^{11,12} The resultant mixture of reactive monomers was a viscous liquid at room temperature and contained no residual solvent. And due to the oligomeric amine, the resultant polyimide oligomer produced a highly branched and nonsymmetric material which exhibited better flow. This technology was given the name LARC-160 by its developers.

The next developmental program pertaining to the thermosetting polyimide was done by Hughes Aircraft Company under an Air Force contract in 1969.^{13,14,15} The approach they took was to incorporate an end capping functionality which would lead to a more thermal stable crosslinking point

than the ones obtained from the thermal polymerization of PMR-15 and LARC-160. Work at Hughes resulted in the addition of acetylene end capper, aminophenyl acetylene, and the use of a new diamine, bis(aminophenoxy)benzene, into a polyimide system. The reasoning for these modifications was that it was felt that the use of the acetylene end capper would form the more thermal stable benzene moiety through the thermal induced trimerization of the acetylene functionality. It was later shown that only a small portion of the acetylene end capper actually trimerized to a benzene moiety.¹⁶ And the new diamine used was a meta substituted compound; this was thought to reduce the brittleness of the resultant cured material. The acetylene terminated polyimide was known as Thermid[®] 600. The name was later changed to Thermid MC600 when the technology was licensed to Gulf Oil Chemical Company. Gulf expanded the product line to include the acetylene terminated amic acid version, LR600, and the monomeric mixture of reactants, AL600.

In 1972, DuPont expanded their polyimide line by introducing a series of thermoplastic polyimides, NR 150.¹⁷ This series of polyimides was based on the reaction of 2,2-bis(3,4-dicarboxyphenyl) hexafluoropropane with phenylenediamine (95 mole % para and 5 mole % meta). The change in dianhydride to a partially fluorinated version was done to improve both the processability and thermal stability of the final polyimide. Monomeric lacquer varnish of this chemistry was available at one time for prepregging; however, the material was pulled off the market and only supplied to customers making specific parts under government contracts. Recently DuPont has reoffered this material to various aerospace companies.

During the early seventies Upjohn entered the commercial polyimide field with the introduction of Polyimide 2080.^{18,19} This polyimide was synthesized via a different route than the previously mentioned polyimides. Upjohn's material was formed from a mixture of tetracarboxylic dianhydrides by condensation with diisocyanates with the subsequent loss of carbon dioxide and water.

TRW has also introduced partially fluorinated polyimides for high temperature performance composite applications. Rather than having a fluorinated dianhydride, their partially fluorinated polyimides are based on a fluorine containing diamine, 2,2-bis[4-(4-aminophenoxy)phenyl] hexafluoropropane, 4-BDAF.^{20,21} TRW has two formulated polyimides. For use up to 600°F they recommend their polyimide based on 4-BDAF with BTDA and for temperatures above 600°F, 4-BDAF with PMDA.

Chem-tronics also introduced a series of thermoplastic polyimides under the name Chem-Lon. This series of polyimides was formed from an exchange reaction between a bisimide monomer and an aromatic diamine.²²

The acetylene terminated polyimide chemistry developed by Hughes has been modified to include an isomeric form of the imide, the isoimide.²³ This isoimide form was developed to improve on the processability and solubility of the acetylene terminated oligomers. The isoimide form is much more soluble in common organic solvents and exhibits better melt flow properties in comparison to the corresponding imide. Also, it is believed that once fully cured, the isoimide precursor yields the same cured structure as the imide. The thermal activities associated with the isoimide during processing consist of the thermal rearrangement of the isoimide form to the imide followed by the thermal crosslinking of the acetylene end capper. The original Thermid materials and the new isoimide version has been licensed to National Starch and Chemical Corporation.

In addition to reintroducing NR150 chemistry to the market place, DuPont has developed a new experimental thermoplastic polyimide called

K-Polymer.²⁴ The monomers used to make up the K-Polymer has not been announced in the open literature.

Besides the previously mentioned commercially available polyimide systems, it should be noted that there are two polyimide copolymers. One is an amide imide known as Torlon marketed by Amoco²⁵, and the other an ether imide under the trade name Ultem marketed by General Electric.²⁶

Processing and Typical Mechanical Properties of Polyimides

In this section, the discussion pertaining to the processing of polyimides will be limited to typical examples of curing schedules. These schedules may not represent the optimal conditions for curing. In some cases the optimal conditions have been developed; however, this type of information is very proprietary to the processors of polyimides for structural composites and is not available in the open literature. This section is only meant to acquaint the reader with general curing conditions and mechanical properties one obtains for the polyimides.

In the processing of polyimides for structural composite applications, the material is most commonly cured in a similar manner as the epoxies. That is, the polyimides are cured in a vacuum bag within an autoclave. The major differences between epoxy and polyimide curing are the polyimides require higher temperatures, higher pressures, and longer times for curing and in most polyimide systems volatile reaction by-products are evolved during processing, and these volatiles must be removed to insure void-free laminates.

Since DuPont was furnishing the earlier polyimides mainly in a final form which could either be machined or shaped into parts, the first polyimide amenable for autoclave curing was the Skybond system of Monsanto. Laminates using this system were cured first by β -staging the prepreg in an oven at 121-177°C (250-350°F). Then the β -staged material was vacuum bagged and placed in an autoclave under a full vacuum (30" Hg). The material was then heated to 177°C (350°F) using a heating rate of 1-2°C/min. Once the temperature reached 121°C (250°C) a pressure of 100 psi was applied. The material was held at 177°C (350°F) for one hour, after which it was cooled to room temperature under vacuum and pressure. To obtain optimal properties, it was recommended to post cure the laminate four hours at each of the following temperatures; 204°C (400°F), 260°C (500°F), 316°C (600°F), and 343°C (650°F) under a nitrogen atmosphere. Typical flexural strengths of fiberglass reinforced Skybond laminates cured using this schedule ranged from 65,000 to 75,000 psi tested at 24°C (75°F). Aging the laminates at 288°C (550°F) for 100 hours reduced the flexural strengths to approximately 37,000 psi; while continued aging at 288°C (550°F) up to 500 hours showed no further loss in mechanical properties.⁷

The most widely studied cure cycle for a polyimide has been achieved with PMR-15. Various projects have been funded by both industrial and governmental monies to optimize the curing of PMR-15. One of the earlier adapted curing schedule involved first consisted of predrying the graphite prepreg at 135°C (275°F) for two hours. Then the material was vacuum bagged, and cured in an autoclave. The temperature was raised under a vacuum pressure of 30"Hg on the bag to 204°C (400°F) at 2.9-3.4°C/min. At 204°C (400°F) a pressure of 200 psi was applied and the material was held at this temperature and pressure for one hour. The temperature was then raised to 316°C (600°F) at 1.8-2.9°C/min. and held for two hours, then cooled to ambient conditions under pressure and vacuum. The laminates were post-cured under pressure in a press for 16 hours at 316°C (600°F). Typical values of

composite mechanical properties of PMR-15 graphite laminates were 190,000 psi ultimate flexural strength tested at room temperature, and 105,000 psi at 316°C (600°F). Flexural modulus was 16.5×10^6 psi at room temperature, and when tested at 316°C (600°F) a modulus of 14.6×10^6 psi was obtained. Short beam shear values at room temperature were 11,700 psi and at 316°C (600°F) 4,600 psi.²⁷ In addition to this 316°C (600°F) curing schedule for PMR-15, Boeing evaluated a 330°C (625°F) and a 288°C (550°F) cure cycle. Based on their studies they are using the 330°C (625°F) cure cycle for the development of their PMR-15 data base. As a result of their study, they felt significant property penalties incurred if the autoclave cure temperature was 288°C (550°F). The overall isothermal and thermal mechanical properties of PMR-15 graphite composites appeared to be sensitive to the cure temperature of the PMR-15 resin.²⁸

One good informational source for polyimide curing is a NASA Langley technical report discussing in detail the manufacturing of LARC-160 graphite laminates. This report describes all steps in the process from the making of the lacquer resin to the testing procedures of the final cured laminates. The curing scheme for LARC-160 is a two step-two vacuum bag schedule. The first step involves the β staging of the laminate in a vacuum bag in an oven to form the imide oligomer and to remove volatile reaction by-products. The second step consists of the thermal crosslinking of the end cappers in the autoclave. The β staging is performed by first placing a vacuum bag assembly of the laminate in an oven and raising the temperature to 107°C (225°F) at a rate of 1.5°C/min. The material is held at 107°C (225°F) for 30 minutes. After which the vacuum in the bag is increased to 28" Hg and the temperature is increased to 232°C (450°F) at 1.5°C/min. At 232°C (450°F) the oven is turned off and the laminate is allowed to cool to 65.6°C (150°F) before the pressure is released. The β -staged material is rebagged and placed in an autoclave. A full vacuum is applied to the bag at the start of the cycle and maintained until the cycle is completed. Also, at the start of the cycle an autoclave pressure of 5 psi is applied. The temperature of the laminate is raised from room temperature to 232°C (450°F) at a maximum rate of 3°C/min. After 15 minutes at 232°C (450°F), additional pressure is applied to 200 psi over a ten minute time period. The laminate is held at 232°C (450°F) an additional 30 minutes, after which heating continued to 332°C (630°F) and held for three hours. The laminate is then cooled to 65.6°C (150°F) under full vacuum and pressure. The pressure is first released, followed by the release of the vacuum. Graphite laminates prepared by this method were reported to be void free, to have excellent thermo-oxidative stability up to 315°C (600°F) and was 40% lighter than aluminum. The mechanical properties measured at 23°C (73°F) with unidirectional fiber orientation included an ultimate tensile strength of 200,000 psi, a flexural strength of 250,000 psi, and an interlaminar shear strength of 15,000 psi.²⁹

In the discussion of the three Thermid acetylene terminated polyimide versions (fully imidized, amic acid, and monomeric mixture) only the AL-600 version, monomeric mixture of reactants, will be discussed. The rationale for this is due to its similarity to PRM-15 and LARC-160. In the earlier developmental work of these materials all three have been prepregged, autoclave cured, and gave essentially equivalent mechanical properties. The isoimide form of this chemistry will be discussed later. Once prepreg of AL-600 has been vacuum bagged and placed in autoclave, a full vacuum (28" Hg) is applied to the bag. The laminate is heated to 100°C (212°F) with a 3.2°C/min. heating rate. The laminate is held at that temperature for 30 minutes. It is then heated to 165°C (329°F) using the same heating rate as before and held at that temperature for 40 minutes. The material is then heated to 250°C (482°F) at 3.2°C/min. When the temperature is between 175°C (347°F) and 185°C (365°F) a pressure of 150 psi is applied. After the laminate has been held at 250°C (482°F) for one hour, it is cooled to room

temperature using a 3.2°C/min. cooling rate. At 100°C (212°F) the pressure is released and the vacuum released at room temperature. A free-standing post cure at 371°C (700°F) for 16 hours has been recommended for these materials. Laminates reinforced with graphite fiber unidirectionally should yield typical flexural strengths of 195,000 psi (room temperature testing) and 148,000 psi (316°C testing), flexural modulus of 15×10^6 psi (rt) and 12×10^6 psi (316°C), and short beam shear of 12,100 psi (rt) and 8,000 (316°C).³⁰

Unidirectional fluorinated NR-150 polyimide laminates have been prepared using vacuum bag autoclave curing techniques. The cycle recommended from this material is to first apply a full vacuum on the bag, heat from room temperature to 130°C (266°F) at 2°C/min. After a 30 minute hold, 200 psi of pressure is applied over a 15 minute period. After the autoclave has been pressurized, it is held an additional 30 minutes at this temperature. Then the laminate is heated to 371°C (700°F) at 0.5°C/min. and held at 371°C (700°F) for 12 hours, after which the laminate is cooled to room temperature under pressure and vacuum. No post cure has been recommended for these laminates. Laminates cured in this manner showed flexural strengths of 230,000 psi (room temperature testing) and 128,000 psi (at 316°C); flexural modulus of 15×10^6 both at room temperature and at 316°C; short beam shear of 15,000 psi (rt) and 7,000 psi (316°C). Thermal oxidative stability for NR-150 glass and quartz fiber laminates has also been reported in terms of times for 50% retention of flexural strengths. These values are 50,000 hours at 260°C (500°F), 5,000 hours at 316°C (600°F), 1,500 hours at 343°C (650°F), and 400 hours at 371°C (700°F).³¹

The isoimide version, IP-600, of the acetylene terminated polyimide has been reported to be an easier processable material in comparison to the other members of the Thermid class and other polyimides. Also, since this material is in an oligomeric form, no volatile reaction by-products should be given off during curing. The autoclave cure cycle of this material consists of heating the vacuum bag assembly under full vacuum to 121°C (250°F) with a heating rate of 3°C/min. The laminate is held at 121°C (250°F) for two hours. Then it is heated to 177°C (350°F) at 3°C/min. At 177°C (350°F) 200 psi of pressure is applied within five minutes, then heating is resumed to 218°C (425°F) at the 3°C/min. The laminate is held at 218°C (425°F) for two hours, then cooled in room temperature with a cooling rate of 3°C/min. At 93.5°C (200°F) the pressure is released and at room temperature the vacuum is released. A post-cure cycle at 371°C (700°F) has also been recommended for this material. Since one of the thermal events associated with the isoimide material is the rearrangement of the isoimide to the imide, in principle all Thermid materials should give the same final cured structures. Thus, upon curing and post-curing, the isoimide should yield similar mechanical properties as the previously mentioned AL-600 version.³⁰

The preliminary autoclave cycle for the experimental K-Polymer polyimide calls for a final molding temperature and time of 343°C (650°F) and three hours at pressures as low as 100 psi. The room temperature flexural strength of unidirectional graphite laminates using a vacuum bag-press molding technique was 206,000 psi with an 88% retention at 121°C (250°F) and an 83% retention at 177°C (350°F). Flexural modulus was reported to be 18×10^6 psi at all testing conditions. Short beam strength of 16,000 psi was measured at room temperature. Retentions of this property was 72% at 121°C (250°F) and 49% at 177°C (350°F).²⁴

In addition to discussion the chemistries, the various curing cycles of some of the commercially available polyimide and typical mechanical properties one can achieve with the polyimides, the reader should be made

aware of several other factors pertaining to the polyimides. One factor deals with the processing of polyimides and should be reemphasized. That is, most of the cycles and mechanical properties reported in this survey by no means reflect the best values one can obtain with these materials. New techniques, such as Internal Bag Pressurization, have been used to produce polyimides with less voids than a "standard" vacuum bag autoclave curing technique. This technique has given laminates with higher mechanical properties and better thermooxidative stability.³² Also, blending of a thermosetting polyimide with a thermoplastic polyimide has been shown to enhance processing behaviors without sacrificing mechanical properties.³³ Also, it should be pointed out that it is difficult to make a valid comparison between the available polyimide systems due to the fact that some are thermoplastic, while they are thermosetting. And the variables one can encounter in preparing structural composite laminates are so numerous that one slight variation can affect the overall performance of laminates significantly.

The major criterion one should use in evaluating the polyimides as a matrix resin for structural composites is their high temperature performance. Most have demonstrated their ability to be used continuously in the 288-316°C (550-600°F) temperature range. While several have been exposed to temperatures ranging from 593-760°C (1,100-1,400°F) for short periods of time. The key to performance is in the processing and there are still areas of development available to achieve maximum upper temperature capabilities of this polymeric family.

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